

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

OBTAINING A HUMATE PRODUCT FROM BROWN COAL

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Abstract

Since the Republic of Kazakhstan is also engaged in agriculture, today the development of Agriculture in the country is one of the main issues. In this regard, in order to improve the situation with economic and social problems, it is necessary to increase agricultural production. The only way to solve this problem is the production of Humate fertilizers. The way to increase the humus content of irrigated lands is to increase the fertility of the soil if we use humic acid salts, i.e. humates, as well as mineral fertilizers with a Humate component, processed from brown coal. Thus, agricultural efficiency can be increased. It can be considered a solution to the problem of providing food to a constantly growing population. Our goal is to produce Humate-containing fertilizers. In this article, research work on obtaining Humate without additives in laboratory conditions is considered. Using the properties of humic substances contained in coal insoluble in acids, we purify the substances contained by acidification and extract a pure Humate product.

Keywords: Humate, Fertilizer, Mineral, nitric and phosphoric acid, sodium hydroxide, extraction, brown coal.

In order to increase agricultural production in the country, it is necessary to consider the use of complex fertilizers, but the production of fertilizers is not fully implemented in the country. In accordance with it, some fertilizers are imported from foreign countries. It is possible to produce the same fertilizers in our country, and the reserves of the necessary raw materials are not a problem. Our goal is to obtain Humate-containing mineral fertilizers.

In the process of growing agricultural products, which are used as products in life, various mineral fertilizers are used. The use of complex-mixed mineral fertilizers containing nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium-trace elements and Humate has a good effect on crop growth.

The Republic of Kazakhstan produces a huge amount of agricultural products, the acreage of which is many hectares of land. A large part of it is made up of grain products. Traditional methods of analysis of the obtained products used in laboratory conditions were carried out [1].

For example, if we take grain products, we get an average of 14.3 C/ha per hectare, and to increase the yield, it is necessary to intensify agricultural production.

The most necessary ways include the use of various fertilizers, effective and timely application of water problems, chemical protection of plants and increasing the fertility of the land.

To increase soil fertility, it is necessary to increase the amount of humus contained in the Earth, increasing

the amount of humus with fertilizer covers only 16-20% of our land [2].

The way to increase the humus content of irrigated lands is the use of humic acid salts, i.e. humates, processed from brown coal, as well as mineral fertilizers with a Humate component, which increase soil fertility.

Oxidized brown coal contains humic substances 41-85%, as well as sulfur, nitrogen, phosphorus, calcium, iron and trace elements cobalt, manganese, nickel, molybdenum, copper.

Similar fertilizers were tested in the fields of neighboring states Uzbekistan, Bashkortostan, Russia and the states of Urain. The Ukrainian state tested the mineral fertilizers with the addition of lignite itself. According to the results of the economy, the yield was 30-40% of peas, 16-38% of beets, 15% of corn, and 48% of corn.

Based on the above facts, it can be seen that the use of mineral fertilizers with a Humate component can increase agricultural production.

And the raw material reserves of Humate-containing mineral fertilizer are sufficient in the country, the use of which does not cause problems.

One of the economic and social problems of the Republic of Kazakhstan is the development of complex mineral fertilizer industries. The degree of use of primary raw materials and waste as fertilizers in the chemical and mining industries is low. Therefore, one of the most pressing issues is the study of ways to obtain Humate-containing mineral fertilizers from natural raw materials and industrial waste.

Today, on the way to solving the problem of food supply to the constantly growing population, increasing the biological productivity of the Earth, developing it is an urgent problem today. Therefore, one of the main elements of soil fertility is the presence of humic substances in the composition. The only way to solve this problem is the production of Humate fertilizers. With the independence of Kazakhstan, it is also important to use local natural resources and industrial waste, to solve them in a new way in a comprehensive manner, to master new technological processes. These are technological searches for more complete processing of raw materials and extraction of Humate from coal waste. The Humate substances we are studying are the remains of disused brown coal. Kazakhstan, being a raw material for obtaining Humate, now uses expensive organic dressings imported from abroad. If we get a Humate-containing mineral fertilizer from the waste of domestic raw materials, it will be cheaper, and we will also contribute to the purification of the environment. The use of Humate fertilizers for plants increases the yield and quality of agricultural crops in the country [3].

The humic substances contained in coal were mixed for 1 hour in a magnetic mixer in a ratio of 1:10 to 1.094 mol/L of brown coal with HNO_3 (nitric acid)

and 1.401 mol/L of H_2SO_4 (sulfuric acid) in order to obtain pure coal, using the property of insoluble in acids.

The mixed coal solution was thoroughly washed with distilled water and dried with filter paper on the drying rack. We reduce the weight of the coal residue that was with the filter paper, that is, we calculate the net weight of the coal residue.

After acidification, the dried coal residue is extracted in a solution of NaOH (sodium hydroxide).

At the end of extraction, the solution is precipitated and filtered using paper in a strainer. In order for the filtration process to run very slowly, distilled water is poured into the filter over the precipitated solution and the sediment is washed out.

Therefore, we reduce the weight of the undissolved residue from the initially obtained brown coal, the acid-soluble substances pass into the acid composition and purify the residue with water. After extraction of the dried residue, we dry it and weigh it. A pure Humate substance, that is, 56% Humate was obtained from 100% coal.

X-ray examination of the resulting Humate was carried out and the composition was determined. The Humate composition is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1-radiospectral analysis of Humate

In the course of radiospectral analysis, the elements found in the composition can be seen in Figure 1.

The chemical composition of the sample and a microscopic view of the same captured area are given during microsexing using an electron microscope, i.e. an electron-probe. The microscopic view is presented in the figures

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below.

Figure 2-microscopic view of the sediment

The composition of the resulting Humate was determined in an X-ray examination. The Humate composition is given in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Chemical composition of Humate

Element	(keV)	mass%	Error%	At%	Compound		mass%K
O	0.000	40.25	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.0000
Na K	1.041	26.53	0.45	39.48	Na ₂ O	35.76	50.0886
Al K	1.486	12.84	0.51	16.29	Al ₂ O ₃	24.27	16.6321
Si K	1.739	14.29	0.59	34.81	SiO ₂	30.56	19.9677
S K	2.307	1.25	0.58	2.66	SO ₃	3.12	2.4411
Cl K	2.621	0.67	0.29	0.53	Cl	0.67	1.1274
K K	3.312	0.36	0.33	0.31	K ₂ O	0.43	0.8133
Ca K	3.690	2.57	0.43	4.39	CaO	3.59	6.2766
Fe K	6.398	1.24	0.80	1.52	FeO	1.60	2.6532
Total		100.00		100.00		100.00	

Laboratory materials made according to the research work on the extraction of Humate are shown in Figure 3 below in the form of a diagram.

Figure 3-coal acidification scheme in laboratory conditions

According to the above experience, we repeated the acidification process again and used phosphoric acid and nitric acid instead of nitric acid and sulfuric acid. Brown coal is mixed with 1.094 mol/L HNO_3 (nitric acid) and 1.401 mol/L H_3PO_4 (phosphoric acid) in a magnetic mixer in a ratio of hard: liquid 1:10 for 1 hour.

The mixed coal solution was thoroughly washed with distilled water 2-3 times and dried in a drying cabinet. We measure the weight of the dried coal residue.

After acidification, we weigh the dried weight and extract the remaining coal in a solution of 0.1 N NaOH (sodium hydroxide) in the amount of 1 hour.

At the end of extraction, the solution was precipitated and filtered in a strainer. Therefore, it can be assumed that if 20.5% of undissolved residues were obtained from 100% brown coal, 21.5% of other substances were transferred to the acid composition, and 58% of the pure Humate substance was obtained.

The novelty of the scientific work is that for the production of Humate fertilizers, experimental laboratory research work was carried out in order to determine the content of humic substances in Brown coals found in the country. To extract Humate from brown coal, work was first carried out to decompose coal in acid. In the first laboratory work, work was carried out to decompose nitric acid and sulfuric acid, K:C in a ratio of 1:10, using the insoluble properties of Humate in acids.

Purified coal was extracted in a solution of sodium hydroxide, resulting in 56% Humate. In the second laboratory work, we performed extraction work using nitric acid and phosphoric acid. A pure Humate substance with a Humate yield of 58% was obtained.

The amount of humic substance found in Brown coals in the country can be used to obtain Humate-containing fertilizers. If we use low-color coal, which is not suitable for burning, in Humate fertilizer, we will help to improve the environmental and economic situation of the country.

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